

Gender Differential Analysis of Social Intelligence among Undergraduate Students in Punjab

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The current study examined gender differences in social intelligence among undergraduate students from six colleges in Punjab's Malwa region, including Ludhiana, Patiala, and Moga districts. The Social Intelligence Scale by Chadha and Ganesan (2009) and a self-structured demographic profile questionnaire were used to evaluate 620 respondents, who were distributed equally between males and females. The eight dimensions of social intelligence, i.e., patience, cooperation, confidence, sensitivity, social environment identification, tactfulness, sense of humour, and memory were assessed. For data analysis, statistical methods like the t-test, Z-test, mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage were used. The results showed that there were notable gender differences in the memory, tactfulness, and sensitivity dimensions, with females scoring higher in these domains. Females possessed greater patience at both the low and high levels, whereas males reported higher levels at the medium level. Disparities in sense of humour, confidence, cooperativeness, and recognition of the social environment were largely insignificant. Overall, the findings indicated that females' social intelligence was marginally greater than males, but not statistically significant. In order to promote students' mental health, interpersonal effectiveness, and future professional success, the study emphasizes the complex role that gender plays in forming social intelligence and the necessity of cultivating these abilities in family and educational settings.

Keywords: Social intelligence, gender differences, undergraduate students

Human existence and fulfilment rely heavily on our ability to interact socially. Social interactions are necessary in our daily lives because they allow us to function in public, school, and corporate settings, create and sustain relationships, and relate correctly to people around us (Ryan et al., 2016). Social skills, the underlying social cognition necessary for these skills, and the neurological circuitry that regulates these abilities do not emerge at birth, but rather develop throughout time, from early infancy to adolescence and beyond (Zamani et al., 2019).

Social intelligence is critical in shaping one's life. Thorndike introduced the concept of social intelligence in the early twentieth century, causing a significant shift in our understanding of human intellect. He described social intelligence as the ability to relate and understand, interact with others in a flexible manner (Thorndike, 1920). It is the capacity to cope with other people's feelings, ideas, and behaviours in social or interpersonal situations while simultaneously responding appropriately to the context of such understanding (Marlowe, 1986). Individuals' ability to navigate intricate social ties and form connections enables them to clearly articulate their ideas and get acceptance from others, enabling happy partnerships (Narang et al., 2020).

Gardner's approach supports the idea that social intelligence is an

important aspect of human development that can be improved through learning and social interactions (Arghode, 2013). In Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, interpersonal intelligence is integrally tied to social intelligence, which is defined as the ability to understand, empathise with, and effectively engage with others and those with strong interpersonal intelligence can recognize the ideas, motivations, and intentions of others, allowing them to successfully navigate social situations (Gardner, 1983).

A person's success is more dependent on social intelligence than cognitive intelligence, thus he will succeed if he interacts well with others (Kriemeen & Hajaia, 2017). As a result, social intelligence is valuable since it enables people to operate delicately and confidently. The attempt to replicate spending quality time with family members is intended to boost social intelligence by providing a sense of security and confidence (Huda & Salem, 2022). Instilling social intelligence in familial situations promotes societal outcomes.

Social intelligence in childhood influences an individual's future personal, intellectual, and professional success. It teaches children how to interpret emotions, manage relationships, and adapt to different social situations, all of which will be essential later in life (Goleman, 2006). Individuals with high social intelligence are more likely to create pleasant relationships, excel at collaborative work, and deal effectively with life's challenges (Bar-On, 2006). Early social intelligence is linked to emotional well-being and resilience in adulthood (Zamani et al., 2019). Thus, developing social intelligence from an early age lays the framework for a prosperous, emotionally healthy, and socially competent adulthood.

Method

Participants

The sample included 620 undergraduate students aged 20-22 years, equally distributed between males and females. The study was

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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conducted within six colleges of Ludhiana, Patiala and Moga districts of Malwa region of Punjab.

Measures

Undergraduates' information was obtained using both standardized and self-structured instruments, as follows:

Demographic Profile Questionnaire: The undergraduates' socio-personal characteristics were collected using a self-structured demographic profile questionnaire, which included age, gender, birth order, family type, family size, parents' educational background, and occupation.

Social Intelligence Scale: The social intelligence scale formulated by Chadha and Ganesan (2009) was used to measure social intelligence. The scale has 66 items in 8 dimensions, which are explained as follows:

Patience- It is the ability to remain calm in the face of a stressful event.

Co-operativeness- Ability to engage with others in an appropriate way to see things from multiple perspectives.

Confidence Level- A strong belief in oneself and one's prospects.

Sensitivity - Being intensely aware of and receptive to human behaviour.

Recognition of Social Environment - The ability to understand the character and atmosphere of a given scenario.

Tactfulness - Refers to a delicate judgement of what is appropriate to say or do.

Sense of Humor - The ability to experience and cause amusement; to see the bright side of life.

Memory - The ability to recall all pertinent concerns, including names and faces of people.

The scale consists of 8 dimensions with 66 items. Dimensions were assessed using a multiple choice technique except for tactfulness, where the responses were in the form of 'Yes' or 'No' and memory was scored 1 or 0 based on whether the subject's response was correct or incorrect. The scale's reliability was determined using split-half and test-retest methods. The split-half

reliability coefficients ranged from 0.89 to 0.96, and the test-retest reliability coefficients ranged from 0.84 to 0.97, reflecting the scale's high level of internal consistency and stability.

The total scores on the scale were computed to ascertain students' overall social intelligence using the following three levels:

S.No.	Levels of Social Intelligence	Range of Raw Scores
1	Low	≤69
2	Medium	70-103
3	High	>103

Data Collection

After clarifying the study's objectives with the principals, permission was granted to collect data. The questionnaires were handed to the students following an explanation of the study's goal. They were asked to provide accurate responses and were promised that their details would be kept anonymous and that the data received would only be utilized for research purpose.

Statistical Analysis

A range of statistical methods were used, including frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test, and Z-test.

Results

Gender Wise Distribution of Respondents across Various Dimensions and Levels of Social Intelligence

Table 1 and Figure 1 depict the gender distribution of social intelligence among 620 students, which is classified into various dimensions such as patience, cooperativeness, confidence, sensitivity, recognition of social environment, tactfulness, sense of humour, and memory. Each dimension is divided into three levels: low, medium, and high, with corresponding frequencies and percentages. The frequencies and percentages for each level are shown for male and female respondents (n=310 each). The table also shows z-values, which indicate the statistical significance of the disparities between the genders.

Table 1

Gender Wise Distribution of Respondents across Various Dimensions and Levels of Social Intelligence

Dimensions of social intelligence		Gender (n=620)				Z
		Males (n _i =310)		Females (n _i =310)		
		f	%	f	%	
Patience	Low	44	14.19	65	20.97	2.218*
	Medium	248	80.00	201	64.84	4.223**
	High	18	5.81	44	14.19	3.478**
Co-operativeness	Low	23	7.42	46	14.84	2.937**
	Medium	141	45.48	126	40.65	1.214
	High	146	47.10	138	44.52	0.645
Confidence	Low	54	17.42	54	17.42	0.000
	Medium	225	72.58	234	75.48	0.823
	High	31	10.00	22	7.10	1.291
Sensitivity	Low	43	13.87	34	10.97	1.095
	Medium	214	69.03	196	63.23	1.526
	High	53	17.10	80	25.81	2.642**

Recognition of social environment	Low	39	12.58	40	12.90	0.119
	Medium	243	78.39	248	80.00	0.494
	High	28	9.03	22	7.10	0.882
Tactfulness	Low	48	15.48	35	11.29	1.532
	Medium	253	81.61	257	82.90	0.420
	High	9	2.90	18	5.81	1.775
Sense of humor	Low	60	19.35	56	18.06	0.412
	Medium	230	74.19	227	73.23	0.272
	High	20	6.45	27	8.71	1.063
Memory	Low	18	5.81	2	0.65	3.634**
	Medium	108	34.84	96	30.97	1.025
	High	184	59.35	212	68.39	2.343*
Overall social intelligence	Low	6	1.94	14	4.52	1.817
	Medium	179	57.74	161	51.94	1.451
	High	125	40.32	135	43.55	0.815

Note. *Significant at the 0.05 level, **Significant at the 0.01 level

Patience

Data on patience, dimension of social intelligence indicated significant variations between males and females at all levels. The study discovered that males significantly ($Z=4.22, p\leq 0.01$) exhibited a considerably larger proportion of patience (80%) than females (64.84%) at the medium level. Females (20.97%) had lower levels of patience than males (14.19%), with a statistically significant difference ($Z=2.21, p<0.01$). Females (14.19%) had a higher percentage at high level than males (5.81%), with a statistically significant gender difference ($Z=3.47, p\leq 0.01$).

Cooperativeness

The study found a significant ($Z=2.93, p\leq 0.01$) difference in low level of cooperation between males and females. Females (14.84%) exceeded males (7.42%) at the low level. No significant differences were found between medium and high levels. At medium level males exhibited a higher percentage (45.48%) than females (40.65%). Similarly, at the high level, male counterparts (47.10%) outperformed female counterparts (44.52%), indicating better cooperation.

Confidence

There were no statistically significant differences in confidence levels across genders. The medium level was most common in both males and females, with females having a higher percentage (75.48%) than males (72.58%). On the other hand, both males and females reported the same level of low-level confidence (17.42%). A significant disparity was identified, with males (10%) indicating a higher level of confidence than females (7.10%).

Sensitivity

The study found a significant gender difference ($Z=2.64, p\leq 0.01$) with a high level of sensitivity. Female respondents (69.03%) reported a higher percentage of sensitivity than male respondents (63.23%) at the high level. Insignificant differences have been observed between the low and medium levels. At the medium level, males (69.03%) showed higher percentage of sensitivity than females (63.23%), indicating a comparable difference. Similarly, at the low level, males (13.87%) exceeded females (10.97%).

Recognition of the Social Environment

There were no significant gender differences in this dimension. The medium level dominated both genders, with females accounting for a greater percentage (80%) than males (78.39%). Males (12.58%) and females (12.90%) reported nearly equal proportions at the low level. At the high level, males (9.03%) outnumbered females (7.10%) in terms of social awareness.

Tactfulness

There were no significant gender disparities in the tactfulness results at any level. Female respondents reported a slightly greater percentage of tactfulness (82.90%) than male respondents (81.61%), with the majority of respondents expressing tactfulness at the medium level. On the other hand, at the low level, males reported being more tactful (15.48%) than females (11.29%). At high level, females (5.81%) exceeded males (2.90%).

Sense of Humour

The data analysis revealed no significant gender differences in sense of humour. Males reported a higher proportion (74.19%) than females (73.23%), with a higher number of respondents reporting at medium level. Males reported a higher percentage (19.35%) than females (18.06%) at a low level. At high level, it was found that females accounted for a larger proportion (8.71%) than males (6.45%).

Memory

The data analysis revealed significant gender disparities between low and high levels of memory, except the medium level, where there was no significant gender difference. Females (68.39%) had significantly higher memory scores ($Z=2.34, p\leq 0.01$) than males (59.35%). At the low level, males (5.81%) outnumbered females (0.65%), with a statistically significant difference ($Z=3.63, p\leq 0.01$). As a result, males had a higher proportion (34.84%) of memory than females (30.97%) at the medium level, although the difference was not statistically significant.

Overall Social Intelligence

The results on overall social intelligence found insignificant differences across all levels. The higher proportion indicated a

medium level of social intelligence, with males reporting a higher number (57.74%) than females (51.94%). In contrast, females reported a higher proportion (43.55%) than males (40.32%) at the high level. Similarly, females exceeded (4.52%) males (1.94%) at a low level of overall social intelligence.

Figure 1

Gender Wise Distribution of Respondents across Various Dimensions and Levels of Social Intelligence

Gender Wise Differences in the Mean Scores (± S.D) of Respondents across Various Dimensions of Social Intelligence

Table 2 and Figure 2 indicate gender differences in mean scores for social intelligence dimensions such as patience, cooperativeness, confidence, sensitivity, recognition of social environment, tactfulness, sense of humour, and memory among 620 respondents (310 males & 310 females). Each dimension's mean and standard deviation (S.D.) are presented, as well as the t-value, which indicates how significant the difference between respondents' means appears.

Table 2 and Figure 2 exhibit the gender variations in respondents' mean scores in various dimensions of social intelligence. Statistically significant differences were observed in sensitivity, tactfulness, and memory. The mean sensitivity scores were nearly equal in both males (19.39±2.44) and females (19.88±2.57), with statistically significant ($t=2.41, p<0.05$) difference. Females (3.73±1.12) scored considerably higher in tactfulness ($t=2.30, p<0.05$) than males (3.53±1.03). Female respondents had better memory (10.04±1.35) than males (9.61±1.76), showing a significant difference ($t=4.42, p<0.01$).

Table 2

Gender Wise Differences in the Mean Scores (± S.D) of Respondents across Various Dimensions of Social Intelligence

Dimensions of social intelligence	Total respondents (n=620)				t
	Males (n ₁ =310)		Females (n ₂ =310)		
	Mean	SD±	Mean	SD±	
Patience	19.11	2.33	19.39	2.98	1.33
Co-operativeness	24.02	3.83	23.46	4.26	1.71
Confidence	19.17	2.76	19.15	2.72	0.11
Sensitivity	19.39	2.44	19.88	2.57	2.41*
Recognition of Social Environment	1.47	0.83	1.41	0.80	0.93
Tactfulness	3.53	1.03	3.73	1.12	2.30*
Sense of Humour	3.68	1.36	3.63	1.34	0.47
Memory	9.61	1.76	10.04	1.35	3.42**
Overall Social Intelligence	100.06	9.20	100.38	10.83	0.39

Note. *Significant at the 0.05 level, **Significant at the 0.01 level

Figure 2

Gender Wise Differences in the Mean Scores (± S.D) of Respondents across Various Dimensions of Social Intelligence

The remaining dimensions showed non-significant differences. Males and females were found to have nearly same levels of patience (19.11±2.33) and (19.39±2.98). However, the difference was statistically significant, with males having somewhat higher mean cooperativeness scores (24.02±3.83) than females (23.46±4.26). The confidence scores for males and females were almost the same, with mean values of (19.17±2.76) and (19.15±2.72). In a similar vein, there was no discernible difference between males and females in their ability to recognize social cues or settings. Males (1.47±0.83) and females (1.41±0.80) had substantially identical mean scores. Males had slightly higher mean scores for sense of humour (3.68±1.36) than females (3.67±1.34), with negligible differences.

Males and females had social intelligence mean scores of (100.06±9.20) and (100.38±10.83, respectively). It was determined that females have a much higher overall level of social intelligence than males.

Discussion

Patience, a characteristic of social intelligence, showed substantial disparities across all levels. Males were shown to be more patient at the intermediate level, whilst females were more patient at both the low and high levels. Patience is directly related to impulse control and self-regulation, which are commonly reinforced in males by cultural expectations to remain composed, repress emotions, and "act strong," especially in traditional family or school settings. Else-Quest et al. (2006) discovered that males exhibit higher degrees of effortful control in organized contexts, contributing to superior behavioral patience.

Another study by Duckworth and Seligman (2006) found that females are better at controlling their urges and accepting delayed rewards, both of which are necessary for patience. Early socialization strategies and expectations that promote females to be less independent and emotionally restrained can contribute to the gender gap in self-control.

The study found significant variations in cooperation, a dimension of social intelligence, revealing that females are more cooperative at low level. Large-scale cross-cultural study indicates that females are more cooperative in social situations, but males may behave differently, particularly in group-based jobs when leadership duties are assumed (Benenson et al., 2007). The prevalence of sensitivity was significantly higher in females, indicating that females are more emotionally sensitive and expressive than males, especially during middle childhood and adolescence, due to both biological and socialization factors (Chaplin & Aldao, 2013). Memory was found to be significantly higher in males at low levels, but females outnumbered males at high levels, which is consistent with research findings by Gurian and Stevens (2005) who discovered that females frequently complete cognitive milestones earlier than males, particularly in language acquisition, verbal fluency, and attention, all of which are required for memory creation and retrieval. Furthermore, females are proven to be more efficient in elaborative encoding processes such as association formation and contextual hint extraction, which increases both short-term and long-term memory retention.

The current study investigated how gender differed in a number of social intelligence domains. It was discovered that females' social intelligence was not significantly higher. Differences in memory, tactfulness, and sensitivity were statistically significant. Due to a combination of biological and socialization variables, previous research has consistently highlighted that females are typically more emotionally receptive, empathic, and sensitive (Karniol et al., 2003). In an identical manner, Chadha and Ganesan (2009) found that females had greater tactfulness scores. It can be concluded that young girls are taught to value social harmony, use courteous communication, and deal with issues subtly skills that enable them to operate diplomatically. Nyberg et al. (2003) discovered that in the memory domain, females consistently outperformed males in verbal and episodic memory tasks, attributing the differences to both neurological and experience factors.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that social intelligence, an important predictor of interpersonal success and adaptability, varies somewhat across gender among college students. Although overall levels of

social intelligence did not differ considerably, females had better memory, sensitivity, and tactfulness, and males had higher patience at the medium level and cooperativeness at specific levels. These distinctions could be attributed to a combination of socialization patterns, cultural expectations, and biological reasons. The findings confirm that social intelligence is not static but rather influenced by early experiences, family environments, and educational situations. Since social intelligence is essential for personal, academic, and professional development, institutions and families should actively cultivate these abilities through supportive interactions, cooperative learning practices, and inclusive environments. Future research could look at the impact of socioeconomic background, cultural values, and developmental phases on social intelligence, providing more insight into how this vital human trait can be improved for overall growth.

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Received September 28, 2025

Revision received October 10, 2025

Accepted October 13, 2025